

Ionic Equilibria in Aqueous Solutions of Cadmium Acetate and the Related Thermodynamic Functions

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The dissociation constants K_1 and K_2 of $\text{CdAc}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CdAc}^+ + \text{Ac}^-$ and $\text{CdAc}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{2+} + \text{Ac}^-$ have been determined from 5° to 35° at 5 intervals from e.m.f. of cells of the type :

where Ac stands for acetate ion. Assuming B_i in $\log \gamma_i = -\frac{AZ^2\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} + B_i\mu$ to be additive and

independent of ionic atmosphere when $\mu < 0.1$, the thermodynamic dissociation constants (K_1 and K_2) of CdAc_2 and CdAc^+ have been calculated. The values of ΔH , ΔS and ΔG° have also been calculated.

FARREL, Ridgeon and Reley¹ found the dissociation constant of $\text{CdAc}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{2+} + 2\text{Ac}^-$ from the potentiometric titrations to vary from 0.63×10^{-2} to 2×10^{-2} and concluded the existence of two stages of dissociation. Quintin^{2,3} reported the existence of associated ions from conductance measurements. Leden⁴ reported the existence of ions from CdAc^+ to CdAc_4^{2-} .

A quantitative study of the thermodynamic dissociation constants of cadmium acetate in dilute solutions at 30°, using salt bridge, was made by Aditya and Prasad⁵. They found the values of dissociation constant of CdAc^+ and CdAc_2 to be 1.7×10^{-2} and 1.0×10^{-1} respectively. Later on Sircar and Prasad⁶ pointed out that a L.J.P. in salt bridges might be higher than 1.0 mV at times. No worker had studied the heat of ionisation (ΔH) and other thermodynamic functions of $\text{CdAc}^+ = \text{Cd}^{2+} + \text{Ac}^-$ and $\text{CdAc}_2 = \text{CdAc}^+ + \text{Ac}^-$. Thus, it was considered worthwhile to determine the dissociation constants of CdAc^+ and CdAc_2 using cells without L.J.P. of the type :

and to calculate ΔH and other thermodynamic functions.

Experimental

A stock solution of acetic acid was prepared by diluting strong acid (G.R., S. Merck) and standardising it with baryta solution standardised with HCl

(standardised with borax⁷). Solutions of a mixture of cadmium acetate and acetic acid (1:1) were prepared by dissolving known quantities of cadmium acetate (A.R.) and stock solution of acetic acid in double distilled water. The amount of cadmium in the solution, estimated by oxine method⁸ agreed excellently with the calculated value. Concentrations were expressed in molality. Cadmium amalgam containing 9 to 11% of cadmium and cadmium amalgam half-cells were prepared as recommended by LaMer and Parks⁹. Mercury/mercurous acetate electrode was prepared as given in an earlier paper¹⁰.

The electrode vessels, bridges and setting up of cells were similar to those published in an earlier paper¹¹. The temperature of the air thermostat was controlled within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Measurements were made with a Tinsley Vernier Potentiometer. The cell with 9% cadmium in cadmium amalgam electrode attained equilibrium within 3 hr. The cells with 11% cadmium in cadmium amalgam attained equilibrium after a longer time at temperatures below 20° but gave the same result. Duplicate experiments, performed in case of each solution never differed by more than 0.1 mV. Experimental and other significant data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Stoichiometric molalities are denoted by m_1 , in the case of HAc and m_2 in the case of CdAc_2 . The molality range has been so chosen that the ionic strength (μ) even in rough calculation does not exceed 0.1.

Discussion

Leaving out charges on the ions the e.m.f. of cells

TABLE I

$m_1 \times 10^3$	$m_2 \times 10^3$	E /abs.volt.	$m_{Cd^{2+}}$ $\times 10^3$	m_{Ac^-} $\times 10^3$	m_{CdAc^+} $\times 10^3$	m_{H^+} $\times 10^5$	$\mu \times 10^8$
Temperature 5°							
8.013	8.013	1.04144	5.659	13.685	2.354	1.3	19.344
9.017	9.017	1.03875	5.963	14.993	3.054	1.3	20.956
10.020	10.020	1.03595	6.362	16.396	3.658	1.4	22.757
11.023	11.023	1.03314	6.831	17.868	4.192	1.4	24.699
12.025	12.025	1.03076	7.221	19.260	4.804	1.4	26.481
13.029	13.029	1.02861	7.578	20.621	5.451	1.4	28.198
14.031	14.031	1.02654	7.951	21.997	6.080	1.5	29.949
Temperature 10°							
8.346	8.010	1.04334	5.505	13.529	2.505	1.4	19.035
9.390	9.011	1.04046	5.836	14.861	3.175	1.4	20.698
10.435	10.015	1.03760	6.224	16.253	3.791	1.4	22.478
11.482	11.019	1.03479	6.662	17.696	4.357	1.5	24.358
12.529	12.024	1.03229	7.062	19.101	4.962	1.5	26.162
13.573	13.026	1.03012	7.401	20.442	5.625	1.5	27.844
14.619	14.030	1.02813	7.715	21.761	6.315	1.6	29.476
Temperature 15°							
8.029	8.026	1.04552	5.347	13.386	2.679	1.4	18.733
9.036	9.033	1.04236	5.723	14.770	3.310	1.4	20.494
10.037	10.033	1.03946	6.100	16.147	3.933	1.4	22.247
11.044	11.039	1.03654	6.547	17.600	4.492	1.4	24.147
12.052	12.047	1.03417	6.878	18.940	5.169	1.5	25.817
13.060	13.055	1.03191	7.219	20.289	5.836	1.5	27.509
14.064	14.058	1.02980	7.555	21.628	6.503	1.5	29.183
Temperature 20°							
8.026	8.026	1.04710	5.324	13.364	2.702	1.4	18.689
9.032	9.032	1.04404	5.664	14.710	3.368	1.4	20.374
10.036	10.036	1.04105	6.053	16.103	3.983	1.4	22.155
11.043	11.043	1.03821	6.461	17.519	4.582	1.5	23.981
12.049	12.049	1.03587	6.773	18.837	5.276	1.5	25.609
13.058	13.058	1.03346	7.153	20.226	5.905	1.5	27.379
14.068	14.068	1.03144	7.445	21.528	6.623	1.5	28.973
Temperature 25°							
8.013	8.013	1.04890	5.265	13.292	2.748	1.4	18.556
9.017	9.017	1.04573	5.614	14.645	3.403	1.4	20.259
10.020	10.020	1.04283	5.959	15.993	4.061	1.4	21.952
11.023	11.023	1.03988	6.379	17.417	4.644	1.5	23.796
12.025	12.025	1.03741	6.714	18.754	5.311	1.5	25.467
13.029	13.029	1.03516	7.023	20.067	6.006	1.5	27.089
14.031	14.031	1.03304	7.331	21.378	6.700	1.6	28.709
Temperature 30°							
8.346	8.010	1.05074	5.168	13.192	2.842	1.4	18.360
9.390	9.011	1.04770	5.466	14.492	3.545	1.5	19.958
10.435	10.015	1.04471	5.811	15.841	4.204	1.5	21.651
11.482	11.019	1.04167	6.232	17.266	4.787	1.5	23.499
12.529	12.024	1.03926	6.527	18.567	5.497	1.6	25.093
13.573	13.026	1.03694	6.840	19.882	6.186	1.6	26.722
14.619	14.030	1.03496	7.081	21.127	6.949	1.6	28.208
Temperature 35°							
8.030	8.025	1.05239	5.089	13.128	2.936	1.4	18.216
9.035	9.025	1.04954	5.325	14.364	3.700	1.4	19.689
10.040	10.029	1.04661	5.633	15.677	4.396	1.5	21.311
11.049	11.042	1.04363	6.008	17.065	5.034	1.5	23.073
12.055	12.048	1.04102	6.340	18.403	5.708	1.5	24.742
13.062	13.054	1.03877	6.608	19.677	6.446	1.5	26.285
14.069	14.060	1.03664	6.877	20.953	7.183	1.6	27.829

TABLE 2

$m_1 \times 10^3$	$m_2 \times 10^3$	E /abs.volt.	m_{Ac} $\times 10^3$	m_{CdAc^+} $\times 10^3$	$m_{Cd^{2+}}$ $\times 10^3$	m_{CdAc_2} $\times 10^3$	$\mu \times 10^3$
Temperature 5°							
44.26	44.26	0.99831	54.65	28.83	12.91	2.518	67.56
46.29	46.29	0.99725	56.62	30.54	13.04	2.708	69.66
49.32	49.32	0.99580	59.43	33.03	13.20	3.092	72.62
52.37	52.37	0.99445	62.18	35.52	13.33	3.519	75.50
55.40	55.40	0.99317	64.92	38.06	13.43	3.900	78.36
58.46	58.46	0.99196	67.64	40.62	13.51	4.332	81.15
60.48	60.48	0.99116	69.52	42.41	13.55	4.518	83.07
Temperature 10°							
44.24	44.24	0.99979	53.49	29.07	12.21	2.960	65.70
46.28	46.28	0.99870	55.44	30.80	12.32	3.156	67.76
49.32	49.32	0.99727	58.14	33.25	12.45	3.625	70.59
52.35	52.35	0.99592	60.80	35.71	12.55	4.094	73.35
55.40	55.40	0.99456	63.61	38.36	12.63	4.415	76.24
58.43	58.43	0.99347	65.97	40.62	12.68	5.136	78.65
60.47	60.47	0.99264	67.85	42.44	12.71	5.321	80.56
Temperature 15°							
44.30	44.30	1.00135	52.76	29.39	11.69	3.225	64.45
46.32	46.32	1.00034	54.52	30.97	11.77	3.576	66.29
49.37	49.37	0.99879	57.34	33.57	11.89	3.915	69.23
52.39	52.39	0.99755	59.72	35.79	11.96	4.637	71.68
55.44	55.44	0.99614	62.55	38.49	12.03	4.923	74.57
58.49	58.49	0.99498	65.00	40.86	12.07	5.557	77.07
61.62	61.62	0.99378	67.65	43.47	12.09	6.057	79.74
Temperature 20°							
44.42	44.42	1.00280	52.51	29.27	11.62	3.527	64.14
46.49	46.49	1.00169	54.43	30.99	11.72	3.780	66.16
49.50	49.50	1.00026	57.01	33.33	11.84	4.326	68.85
52.56	52.56	0.99881	59.77	35.90	11.94	4.725	71.71
55.55	55.55	0.99758	62.23	38.21	12.01	5.327	74.24
58.70	58.70	0.99642	64.68	40.56	12.06	6.081	76.74
61.70	61.70	0.99520	67.34	43.14	12.10	6.460	79.44
Temperature 25°							
44.26	44.26	1.00417	51.78	29.13	11.32	3.802	63.11
46.29	46.29	1.00310	53.59	30.76	11.42	4.115	65.01
49.32	49.32	1.00162	56.17	33.12	11.53	4.676	67.70
52.37	52.37	1.00022	58.76	35.53	11.62	5.227	70.38
55.40	55.40	0.99889	61.34	37.97	11.68	5.745	73.02
58.46	58.46	0.99767	63.83	40.36	11.73	6.366	75.56
60.48	60.48	0.99686	65.53	42.02	11.75	6.707	77.28
Temperature 30°							
44.24	44.24	1.00571	51.28	29.48	10.90	3.862	62.18
46.28	46.28	1.00465	53.03	31.06	10.99	4.239	64.01
49.32	49.32	1.00313	55.62	33.44	11.09	4.789	66.71
52.35	52.35	1.00174	58.14	35.80	11.17	5.382	69.31
55.40	55.40	1.00040	60.71	38.25	11.23	5.922	71.94
58.43	58.43	0.99912	63.25	40.71	11.27	6.451	74.53
60.47	60.47	0.99833	64.89	42.31	11.29	6.869	76.19
Temperature 35°							
44.30	44.30	1.00733	50.67	29.84	10.41	4.045	61.08
46.32	46.32	1.00618	52.54	31.54	10.50	4.280	63.03
49.37	49.37	1.00469	55.05	33.87	10.59	4.912	65.64
52.39	52.39	1.00324	57.63	36.30	10.67	5.428	68.29
55.44	55.44	1.00191	60.10	38.66	10.72	6.060	70.82
58.49	58.49	1.00065	62.58	41.06	10.76	6.668	73.34
61.62	61.62	0.99941	65.14	43.57	10.78	7.265	75.92

of the type :

is given by,

$$E = E^0 - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln m_{\text{Cd}} m_{\text{Ac}}^2 \gamma_{\text{Cd}} \gamma_{\text{Ac}}^2$$

Therefore,

$$\log m_{\text{Cd}} m_{\text{Ac}}^2 = \frac{(E^0 - E)2F}{2.30259RT} + \frac{6A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} - B\mu \quad \dots (1)$$

The values of A on molality scale are taken from the work of Manov, Bates, Hamer and Acree¹².

The scheme of dissociation is assumed as given below in view of the fact that the work has not been done at higher concentrations at which CdAc_3^- and CdAc_4^{2-} would have been formed in appreciable amounts.

Now, applying equation

$$-\log \gamma_i = \frac{AZ_i^2\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} - B_i\mu,$$

the activity coefficient corresponding to 1st and 2nd stages of dissociation may be represented as,

$$\log C \frac{\gamma_{\text{Ac}}\gamma_{\text{Ac}}}{\gamma_{\text{CdAc}_2}} = -\frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} + B_1\mu \quad \dots (2)$$

and

$$\log \frac{\gamma_{\text{Cd}}\gamma_{\text{Ac}}}{\gamma_{\text{CdAc}}} = -\frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} + B_2\mu \quad \dots (3)$$

where $\gamma_{\text{CdAc}_2} = 1$, $B_1 = B_{\text{CdAc}} + B_{\text{Ac}}$ and $B_2 = B_{\text{Cd}} + B_{\text{Ac}} - B_{\text{CdAc}}$. Adding equations (2) and (3), we get,

$$\log \gamma_{\text{Cd}} \gamma_{\text{Ac}}^2 = -\frac{6A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} + B\mu \quad \dots (4)$$

where $B = B_1 + B_2$. Therefore, the sum of B_1 and B_2 should be equal to B in equation (1).

E^0 of the cell in abs.mV calculated from (i) E^0 of mercury/mercurous acetate electrode¹⁰ and (ii) recalculated values of E^0 of $\text{Cd}_x\text{Hg}_y/\text{Cd}^{2+}$ electrode¹³ are given below :

t °C	5	10	15	20	25	30	35
E^0	869.4	867.7	866.2	864.3	862.7	860.9	859.0

Now, upto $m_2 = 0.015$, the first stage of dissociation, $\text{CdAc}_2 \rightarrow \text{CdAc}^+ + \text{Ac}^-$, seems to be complete. If β be the degree of dissociation of CdAc^+ , then,

$$m_{\text{Cd}} = \beta m_2 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$m_{\text{Ac}} = (1 + \beta)m_2 + m_H \quad \dots (6)$$

$$m_{\text{CdAc}} = (1 - \beta)m_2 \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\mu = (1 + 2\beta)m_2 + m_H \quad \dots (8)$$

and

$$m_{\text{Cd}} m_{\text{Ac}}^2 = \beta m_2 \{(1 + \beta)m_2 + m_H\}^2 \quad \dots (9)$$

Now, a rough value using approximate equation,

$$\frac{m_H \times 2m_2}{m_1} = 2.8 \times 10^{-5},$$

is assigned to m_H . Arbitrary values are assigned both to B and μ . Since E the measured value of e.m.f. and E^0 are known the corresponding value of $m_{\text{Cd}} m_{\text{Ac}}^2$ is calculated from equation (1) and that of β from equation (9). A new value of μ is found from equation (8). Without changing the value of B the process is repeated till β becomes constant upto the 4th place of decimal corresponding to assigned value of m_H . Finally, m_H is calculated using equation,

$$\log \frac{m_H m_{\text{Ac}}}{m_{\text{HAc}}} = \log K + \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} - b\mu \quad \dots (10)$$

in which K and b are known¹⁰. If m_H differs upto the 6th place of decimal then the above process is again repeated to have the constant values of m_H and β . In case of each solution the values of m_{Cd} , m_{Ac} , m_{CdAc} and μ are then calculated from equations (5), (6), (7) and (8) respectively and are used in equation (11) given below.

The dissociation constant (K_2) of CdAc^+ is given by

$$K_2 = \frac{m_{\text{Cd}} m_{\text{Ac}}}{m_{\text{CdAc}}} \times \frac{\gamma_{\text{Cd}} \gamma_{\text{Ac}}}{\gamma_{\text{CdAc}}} = K_{A(2)} \frac{\gamma_{\text{Cd}} \gamma_{\text{Ac}}}{\gamma_{\text{CdAc}}}$$

which reduces to

$$\log K_{A(2)} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_2 - B_2\mu \quad \dots (11)$$

where B_2 is the same as in equation (3). The plot of L.H.S. of equation (11) against μ for any temperature when $m_2 < 0.015$ gives a straight line from which B_2 is found. The point at the lowest μ was left out of consideration as gray black colour was formed. This may be due to equilibrium¹⁴ $\text{Hg}_2^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Hg}^{2+} + \text{Hg}$. At higher concentration of Ac^- ion the dissociation¹⁵ of $\text{HgAc}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{Hg}^{2+} + 2\text{Ac}^-$ ($k = 10^{-9}$) is suppressed. The concentration of Hg_2^{2+} is also suppressed due to common ion effect. Hence except at the lowest value of μ the amount of mercury

formed is not large enough to give grey black colour or cause deviation from straight line. we get

Beyond $m_2 = 0.015$, K_2 ceases to be constant on complete

$$\log K_{A(1)} - \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_1 - B_1\mu \quad \dots (20)$$

the basis of $\text{CdAc}_2 \longrightarrow \text{CdAc}^+ + \text{Ac}^-$. Hence, it has to be assumed that the scheme of dissociation is as given earlier.

where B_1 is the same as in equation (2). Now, $K_{A(1)}$ and μ for each solution being known, the values of K_1 and B_1 are found by graphical plots of equation (20).

A suitable range (i.e., when $m_2 = 0.04$ to 0.06) was chosen to calculate the dissociation constant of CdAc_2 . In this range the presence of acetic acid in the solution is ignored as it is found by calculation that it does not introduce any appreciable change in the values of μ and other molality terms upto the 5th place of decimal. If α be the degree of dissociation of CdAc_2 , and β that of CdAc^+ , then

If $B \neq B_1 + B_2$, then a new value equal to approximately $B_1 + B_2$ is assigned to B . This is used in equation (1) now. The whole process is repeated till $B = B_1 + B_2$ upto the 2nd place of decimal and then the corresponding values of K_1 and K_2 are assumed to be correct.

$$m_{\text{Cd}} = \alpha\beta m_2 \quad \dots (12)$$

$$m_{\text{Ac}} = \alpha(1+\beta)m_2 \quad \dots (13)$$

$$m_{\text{CdAc}} = \alpha(1-\beta)m_2 \quad \dots (14)$$

$$m_{\text{CdAc}_2} = (1-\alpha)m_2 \quad \dots (15)$$

$$\mu = (1+2\beta)\alpha m_2 \quad \dots (16)$$

$$m_{\text{Cd}}m_{\text{Ac}}^2 = \alpha^3\beta(1+\beta)^2 m_2^3 \quad \dots (17)$$

and

$$K_{A(2)} = \frac{m_{\text{Cd}}m_{\text{Ac}}}{m_{\text{CdAc}}} = \frac{\alpha\beta(1+\beta)m_2}{(1-\beta)} \quad \dots (18)$$

Thus, from equations (17) and (18),

$$\frac{K_{A(2)}^3}{m_{\text{Cd}}m_{\text{Ac}}^2} = \frac{\beta^2(1+\beta)}{(1-\beta)^3} \quad \dots (19)$$

The assumed values of B in equation (1) has to be used here also. To determine the various molality terms in any solution, an arbitrary value is assigned to μ . The corresponding values of m_{Cd} , m_{Ac}^2 and $K_{A(2)}$ becomes known from equations (1) and (11) respectively. Now, β is found from equation (19), α from equation (18) and a new value of μ from equation (16). The above process is repeated till α and β become constant upto the 4th place of decimal and μ upto the 5th place of decimal. At this stage the various molality terms and μ calculated from equation (12) to (16) are used in equation (20) given below.

Now, the thermodynamic dissociation constant

$$K_1 = \frac{m_{\text{Cd}}m_{\text{Ac}}}{m_{\text{CdAc}}} \times \gamma_{\text{CdAc}}\gamma_{\text{Ac}} \quad (\text{since } \gamma_{\text{CdAc}_2} = 1)$$

Writing

$$K_{A(1)} \text{ for } \frac{m_{\text{Cd}}m_{\text{Ac}}}{m_{\text{CdAc}}},$$

The various molality terms and μ (i) for $m_2 < 0.015$ are given in Table 1 and (ii) for $m_2 = 0.04$ to 0.06 are given in Table 2. The final values of K_1 , K_2 , B , B_1 and B_2 are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

t/°C	5	10	15	20	25	30	35
B	5.20	5.50	5.70	5.35	5.50	5.50	5.50
B ₁	0.28	0.27	0.29	0.19	0.23	0.24	0.30
B ₂	4.92	5.23	5.41	5.16	5.27	5.26	5.20
K ₁ × 10	4.09	3.45	3.09	2.80	2.56	2.48	2.45
K ₂ × 10 ²	2.07	1.94	1.84	1.75	1.69	1.57	1.43

There may be undissociated CdAc_2 at lower concentrations ($m_2 < 0.015$). It may not be enough

to make the plot of $\log K_{A(2)} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$ against μ

depart from linearity but it may affect the values of B_2 and K_2 . Similarly the values of B_1 and K_1 may be affected to some extent due to unmarked presence of CdAc_3^- . Hence B_1 and B_2 found may not be as accurate as we wish them to be. Our accuracy of e.m.f. measurements is ± 0.05 mV. Therefore, the calculated values of K_1 and K_2 should be accurate (mathematically) upto four significant figures. Considering (i) above facts and (ii) some assumptions made in the calculation, these values have been reported upto three significant figures only.

Aditya and Prasad⁵ found $K_1 = 1.0 \times 10^{-1}$ and $K_2 = 1.7 \times 10^{-2}$ at 30° on molar scale. The marked difference between their value and present value of K_1 , may be due to L.J.P. in their cells.

The values of ΔH have been found from the slope of the straight lines obtained by plotting the respective values of $\log K$ against $1/T$. The values of ΔG° at 25° has been found from $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K$

and that of ΔS^0 at 25° from $\Delta G^0 = \Delta H^0 - T\Delta S^0$ (assuming $\Delta H = \Delta H^0$).

Reaction	$-\Delta H$ cals/mole	ΔG^0 cals/mole	$-\Delta S^0$ eu/mole
$\text{CdAc}_2 = \text{CdAc}^+ + \text{Ac}^-$	2800 ± 50	800	12.1
$\text{CdAc}^+ = \text{Cd}^{2+} + \text{Ac}^-$	1830 ± 20	2400	14.2

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